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Chicken Manure Effect on The Growth and Yield of Three Variety Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill.) Grown in Ultisols

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Abstract

Tomatoes are a commodity with considerable economic value and marketing potential in Bengkulu City, Indonesia. Ultisols, which include characteristics such as low pH and soil fertility, occupy the majority of the land in Bengkulu City. Fertilization is required to increase soil fertility. The study aimed to determine the dosage of chicken manure for tomato plant growth and yield and tomato varieties suitable for cultivation in Ultisol. The research was conducted in Bentiring Village, Muara Bangkahulu District, Bengkulu City, Indonesia. A Completely Randomized Block Design (RCBD) with two factors was employed in the study. The results showed an interaction between the dose of chicken manure and varieties on the variables of plant height, shoot dry weight, fruit weight/plant, fruit diameter, and the number of fruit/plant. The dose of chicken manure applied has a significant effect on plant fresh weight. Each tomato variety has a different flowering and harvesting period. Plant height, dry weight, fruit/plant weight, fruit diameter, and the number of fruits/plant all responded differently to increasing the amount of chicken manure. The three tomato varieties, Tymoti, Servo, and Permata, could all be cultivated in Ultisol.

Keywords: *Lycopersicon esculentum*, manure, tomato, ultisols

Introduction

Infertile soil properties, such as Ultisols, are among factors causing low tomato productivity in Bengkulu Province as compared to the national average. Ultisols account for nearly 25% total acreage of soils in Indonesia. In general, Ultisols have low nutrient availability, high acidity, and low cation exchange capacity (Subagyo *et al.*, 2014). According to Subowo (2012), Ultisols is highly potential for agricultural land development to compensate the agricultural land shortage. Most tomato farming practices in Bengkulu use land with a soil order of Ultisols.

Tomato cultivation faces various obstacles to achieve its high productivity. Among others, limiting factors include inappropriate cultivars, insufficient plant nutrition, poor technical culture, and ineffective pest/disease control. According to Barus (2012), the application of manure can improve soil fertility and increase crop yields. Manure contains complete plant nutrients both macro and micro nutrients as well as high CEC. Yetti and Elita (2008) reported that chicken manure contains 1.5% N with moisture content of 57%, thereby increasing the activity of micro-organisms. Chicken manure decomposes relatively quickly, ensuring adequate nutrient availability and faster absorption by plant roots (Hartatik and Widowati, 2010).

Chicken manure is commonly used to enhance tomato growth and yield components. Research by Luthfyrakhman and Susila (2013) showed that the application of chicken manure linearly increased the fruit weight of tomato. This is because chicken manure decomposes quickly and has a higher nutrient content than other livestock manure (Widowati *et al.*, 2005). The nutrient content of chicken manure has 1.00-3.13% N, 2.8-

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6.00% P_2O_5 and 0.40-2.00% K_2O while N nutrient in cow manure is 0.10-0.96 %, P_2O_5 0.64-1.15% and K_2O 0.45-1.00%. In addition, goat manure contains 0.83-0.95% N, 0.35-0.51% P_2O_5 and 1.00-1.20% P_2O_5 .

The application of chicken manure should be adjusted to meet the requirement of plant nutrient for high yield. According to Maria (2016), chicken manure doses of 20 and 30 tons/ha had the highest effect on the number of tillers, plant height, and plant production of *Brachiaria humidicola*. On the other hand, the optimal dose of chicken manure for tomatoes is 24,375 tons/ha (Luthfyrahma and Susila, 2013). This dose determines the highest effect of the chicken manure for hybrid tomato.

In tomato development, the employment of adaptive and high-yielding cultivars is a reasonable option. Up to the present, local varieties dominate cultivated tomato cultivation (Nurita *et al.* 2014). Purwati and Khairunisa (2007) confirmed that the utilization of high-yielding cultivars in the lowlands is closely related to crop improvement and gains in productivity. The use of cultivars with outstanding performance and easily adapted to lowland environment is inevitable to have high productivity. The research objective was to determine the best combination of varieties and doses of manure on the growth and yield of tomato in Ultisols.

Materials and Methods

The research was conducted from January 2019 to April 2019 in Bentiring Village, Muara Bangkahulu District, Bengkulu City, Indonesia.

Experimental Design

The study used a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with two factors. The first factor is tomato variety (V), consisting of Tymoti, Servo, and Permata. The second factor is the dose of chicken manure (P), which consists of 0 tons/ha, 15 tons/ha, and 30 tons/ha. Each treatment combination was repeated three times.

Soil sampling and Analysis

Soil was compositely sampled for 5 sites at the depth of 0-20 cm. Soil sample, then, was air-dried, sieved with 0.5 mm screen, and analyzed for soil pH, organic-C, total- N, available P (Bray I), and exchangeable K.

Field Experiment

Seed Preparation

The study used tomato seeds of the Tymoti, Servo, and Permata varieties. The seeds were sorted by soaking them in water and submerged seed was selected for germination. The seed germination test was carried out using the tissue paper method for three days until emerging their radicles. The nursery media was a 1:1 mixture of soil and manure (v:v). The media was watered every day to maintain its moisture.

Land Preparation and planting

Land preparation was started by clearing and tilled using a hoed to approximately 25 cm depth. After hoeing the soil, a 4 m × 1 m x, 30 cm (l x w x h) experimental plot was constructed. Chicken manure was next applied homogeneously on the soil surface a week before transplanting. The experimental plot was covered using silver-black mulch. Transplanting was conducted after the tomato seedlings was three weeks old, at a 40 cm × 50 cm spacing. Recommended dose of urea, KCl, and SP-36 was applied at planting. Five plant samples were randomly selected on each experimental plot. Selected samples were those located at the middle row of each experimental plot.

Plants were watered twice a day (in the morning and evening) to maintain the soil moisture. Weeding was manually controlled and pest and disease control was preventively performed using insecticides to avoid tomato from being infected by pests and diseases. Tomato harvest started when met ripe requirement which was 60 to 90% of the fruit is reddish yellow and solid.

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Observed variables

Observed variables included plant height (cm), leaf number, stem diameter (mm), flowering time (days), harvest time (days), number of bunches, fruit weight/plant (g), fruit weight (g), fruit diameter, fresh plant weight (g), and shoot dry weight per plant (g).

Data analysis

Data were statistically analyzed using analysis of variance (ANOVA) at the 5% level. The treatments that showed a significant effect were further tested using an orthogonal polynomial and Least Significant Difference (LSD).

Results and Discussion

Research Overview

The experimental site located at Bentiring Village, Muara Bangkahulu District, Bengkulu City, Indonesia with soil characteristics as follows: soil moisture content was 4.04%, pH (H₂O) was 5.30, total-N = 1.06%, organic-C = 4.7%, available P = 31.63 ppm, exchangeable K = 0.06 m³/100g, exchangeable Al = 0.63 me/100g and exchangeable H= 0.42 me/100 g. According to xv. Balai Penelitian Tanah (2005) classification, the soil pH was classified low, exchangeable potassium very low, total N low, the organic-CC moderate, and available P was relatively high. According to Tafajani (2010) tomato grows well at soils with pH of 5.5 to 7, but its growth is hampered at soils with a pH of less than 5.

During the study, the average rainfall from February to April 20019 was 5.85 mm, 14.75 mm, and 15.29 mm, while the average air temperature was 27.26 °C, 27.04 °C, and 27.36 °C, respectively. In general, the optimal rainfall for tomato growth is 100-200 mm/month. Nonetheless, the rainfall below the optimal requirement and the number of rainy days was relatively uneven, so intensive watering was carried out in the morning and evening. Tomato optimal required daily air temperature ranges from 23 to 30°C during the day and 15 to 20°C at night (Agromedia, 2007). Figure 1 shows the performance of tomato at seedlings, at the nursery and in the field.

Figure 1: (a) tomato seedlings at the nursery, (b) tomato plants begin to flower, and (c) tomato performance in the field.

The plant height ranged from 64.8 cm to 101 cm and the fruit weight was 3.945 g/plot or 9.8 tons/ha. This result is lower than the variety potential. Also, it is lower than those cultivated in low or medium altitude land with tomato yield of 49.25 tons/ha (Purwati and Khairunisa 2007). The low yield might be associated with several factors, such as pests and diseases. Armyworm, wilt disease, and fruit rot infected tomato plants (Figure 2).

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Figure 2. Plants infected by Pests and Diseases: (a) armyworm, (b) wilt disease, (c) rotten fruit

At 7 DAP, armyworms began to attack the leaves. This pest attack hollows out the upper surface of the leaves and damages the leaf bones, resulting in an irregular leaf shape. Pest control was done by cutting the damaged leaves and applying a chemical insecticide containing the active ingredient of Deltamethrin at a dose of 2 g/l. Pest control has successfully lowered the incidence of armyworm invasions on plants.

Fungi and bacteria can cause plant wilting. Wilting symptoms in tomato plants are characterized by plants that suddenly wither and die. Fungi and bacteria that attack plants begin with the roots and easily spread to all plant parts. The affected plants were removed and destroyed and this control effectively reduced the disease spread to other plants.

Fruit rot attacked tomato at 28 days after planting (DAP) with a symptom of small wet spots that are round and sunken in shape, brown in color, and eventually turn black. Fruit rot was controlled by removing affected fruit and spraying a fungicide containing the active ingredient Mankozeb at a dose of 2 g/l. The disease infection might be related to climate condition during the study.

Analysis of Variance

Analysis of variance showed that there was an interaction between the dose of chicken manure and the variety on the plant height, dry weight, fruit weight/plant, fruit diameter, and fruit number/plant. The chicken manure significantly affected fresh and dry weight of shoot. There were significant differences on the flowering and harvesting time among the varieties of tomato. The data with a coefficient of variation (CV) value of more than 20% were transformed as seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Summary of F-Calculated Effect of Chicken Manure Dosage on Tomato Varieties

No	Variables	F-calculated			CV (%)
		Interaction (VxD)	Manure dosage (D)	Tomato varieties (V)	
1	Plant height	3.23*	0.04 ^{ns}	0.59 ^{ns}	7.88
2	Leave number	0.87 ^{ns}	0.14 ^{ns}	0.93 ^{ns}	15.20
3	Stem diameter	1.60 ^{ns}	0.66 ^{ns}	1.71 ^{ns}	9.04
4	Flowering time	0.22 ^{ns}	1.12 ^{ns}	15.16*	5.34
5	Harvest time	0.24 ^{ns}	0.09 ^{ns}	174.74*	1.15
6	Flower bunches	2.69 ^{ns}	0.38 ^{ns}	0.30 ^{ns}	12.13
7	Fruit number/plant	3.21*	0.95 ^{ns}	0.80 ^{ns}	16.17
8	Fruit weight/plant	3.72*	0.18 ^{ns}	0.30 ^{ns}	19.81
9	Fruit weight	0.94 ^{ns}	0.75 ^{ns}	2.39 ^{ns}	12.69
10	Fruit diameter	3.32*	2.18 ^{ns}	0.81 ^{ns}	6.74
11	Fruit weight/plot	2.96 ^{ns}	0.36 ^{ns}	0.71 ^{ns}	17.54
12	Shoot fresh weight	2.10 ^{ns}	4.10*	1.0362 ^{ns}	17.51
13	Shoot dry weight	3.06*	7.24*	1.1836 ^{ns}	14.94

Note : *: significantly different, ns: not significantly different, T: transformed data

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Interaction between Tomato Varieties and Chicken Manure Dosage on Plant Height, Plant Dry Weight, Fruit Weight, Fruit Diameter, and Number of Fruits.

The interaction effect between the Tymoti variety and the chicken manure dose resulted in a quadratic pattern with the equation $y = -0.0311x^2 + 0.7644x + 87.867$ and $R^2 = 0.5846$. Fertilizer doses 0 to 15 tons/ha increased plant height, but lowered plant height at dose of 15-30 tons/ha (Figure 3). According to this equation, the optimum manure dose for the Tymoti variety with a maximum plant height of 101.6 cm is 12.3 tons/ha. On the other hand, Servo and Permata varieties form a linear pattern, with the equation $y = -0.4956x + 96.367$ with $R^2 = 0.5053$ and $y = 0.3778x + 79.778$ with $R^2 = 0.2535$, respectively. The higher the dose of manure, the tomato plant height of the Servo variety decreased. In the Permata variety, the higher the dose of fertilizer applied, the higher the plant height.

Figure 3. Interaction of chicken manure and varieties on tomato plant height.

Regression analysis showed that the varieties Tymoti, Servo, and Permata formed a linear pattern with the equation $y = 0.1578x + 12.79$ with the R^2 value of 0.02004, $y = 0.0892x + 16.961$ with the R^2 of 0.0607, and $y = 0.6792x + 9.2644$ with the R^2 of 0.6945. Plant dry weight increased when the dose of chicken manure was increased on the Tymoti, Servo, and Permata varieties (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Interaction of chicken manure and varieties on plant dry weight

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The Orthogonal Polynomial regression showed that the varieties Tymoti, Servo, and Permata formed a linear pattern in a row with the equations $y = -4.214x + 383.68$ with $R^2 = 0.5697$, $y = 1.1038x + 316.29$ with $R^2 = 0.0503$, and $y = 4.7218x + 274.07$ with $R^2 = 0.3319$. In Servo and Permata varieties, increasing the dose of chicken manure increased fruit weight/plant significantly, however in Tymoti, the higher the dose, the lower the fruit weight/plant (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Interaction of chicken manure and varieties on fruit weight/plant.

Orthogonal Polynomial regression analysis showed that the varieties Tymoti, Servo and Permata formed a linear pattern with the equation $y = -0.2177x + 39,088$ with $R^2 = 0.5802$, $y = -0.0992x + 38.353$ with $R^2 = 0.1169$ and $y = 0.0895x + 34.116$ with $R^2 = 0.1811$, respectively. The fruit diameter of the Tymoti variety decreased as the dose of chicken manure was increased. In contrast, the fruit diameter of the Servo and Permata types increased as the dose of manure was increased (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Interaction of chicken manure and varieties on fruit diameter.

The Orthogonal Polynomial regression study revealed that the Tymoti, Servo, and Permata varieties formed a linear pattern, with $y = -0.1156x + 16.6$ and $R^2 = 0.2269$, $y = 0.0667x + 12,533$ and $R^2 = 0.1332$, and $y = 0.1444x + 12.344$ and $R^2 = 0.3431$, respectively. The number of fruits/plants decreased with increasing doses of chicken manure in the Tymoti and Servo tomato varieties; however, in the Permata variety, the higher the dose of chicken manure applied, the more fruit number/plant (Figure 7)

Figure 7. Interaction of chicken manure dosage and varieties on the number of fruits/plants.

The results revealed differences in the response pattern of the various varieties to an increase in the dose of chicken manure applied in the growth and yield components. Plant yield components include fruit weight/plant, fruit diameter, and the number of fruit/plants, whereas growth components include plant height and dry weight. Various responses to manure amongst varieties because each variety was produced using different parents, resulting in a different response to nitrogen absorption in the supplied manure.

Fruit quality is an essential criterion for plant production, as represented by the fruit weight/plant. Farmers' tomato productivity is determined by fruit weight and fruit size. In this study, the treatment dose of manure and variety significantly affected fruit weight/plant and fruit number/plant. Permata variety produced the highest fruit-weight and fruit-number/plant with the application of chicken manure at a dose of 30 tons/ha.

Fruit weight and fruit number are quantitative variables that are influenced by numerous genes and are highly dependent on environmental factors (Zdrakovic *et al.*, 2011). The Permata variety produced the highest fruits number/plants and fruit weight/plant at a dose of 30 tons/ha of chicken manure. The findings of this study are similar to Mariani *et al.* (2017), who reported that applying chicken manure at a dose of 10 tons/ha increased the number of fruit/plant and fruit diameter. Fruit weight is correlated to plant height. Optimal plant height allows for sufficient sunlight to accomplish the photosynthesis process, which produces energy for the production of flowers and fruit. As a result, taller plants will yield a lot more fruit. According to Haydar *et al.* (2007), the taller the tomato plant, the more branches will form, and the production of tomato plants will increase. The maximum plant height achieved in this study was 101.6 cm in the Tymoti variety with a dosage of 12.2 tons/ha of chicken manure. The similar results were reported by Salli and Lehar (2016) in their research on the growth response of several tomato varieties on dry land, and the results showed that the Tymoti F1 variety had the highest plant height and productive branches.

In this study, the difference in fruit diameter was influenced by plant genetic variables that affect fruit production. According to Mangoendijojo (2008), one of the features that can characterize variations among tomato varieties is fruit size, which is quantitatively controlled by numerous genes. Even if these plants are cultivated in the same environment, any differences are due to variables arising from the DNA of individual population members.

Effect of Chicken Manure Dosage on Tomato Plant Growth and Yield

One indicator of plant growth is plant height. Figure 8 shows tomato growth from the first to sixth weeks after transplanting. Weeks 1 to 2 showed insignificant increase in plant height, followed significant increase at weeks 3 to 5 weeks and relatively level off to week 6.

Figure 8. The sigmoid curve of tomato plant height at different doses of chicken manure

Growth is a process of increasing volume due to cell division. Plant height is an indicator of growth to determine the effect of a treatment. According to Purwanto (2011), in general, the process of increasing plant height occurs during the vegetative phase, mainly at the third and fourth weeks, because plants have a good response to absorbing nutrients.

Figure 9 shows the relationship between fresh plant weight and chicken manure dose. Orthogonal polynomial regression analysis showed that increasing the dose of manure was followed by an increase in fresh weight of tomato plants and formed a linear curve pattern with the equation $y = 1,0068x + 46,822$ with $R^2 = 0,6834$. According to the equation, fresh plant weight increased by 15.1 g at every increase in 15 tons/ha of chicken manure.

Figure 9. Effect of chicken manure dosage on plant fresh weight.

Except for fresh plant weight, the application of various doses of chicken manure did not affect tomato plants' growth and yield components in this study (Table 1). This is most likely because the nutrients supplied are not efficiently absorbed by plants. Acidic soil conditions are one of the factors of plant roots' inability to absorb nutrients. The toxicity of Al, Fe, and Mn is the primary constraint to plant growth in acidic soils. The high concentrations of these elements will be detrimental to plant roots. This will also cause plants to be deficient in macronutrients, particularly P, due to the binding of these nutrients by soil particles, rendering their availability to plants. Maryanto and Rahman (2015) reported that a dose of 3.4 kg of chicken manure/plant on Permata variety tomatoes resulted in lower fruit weight when compared to cow manure and Trichoderma fertilizer. Mulyati *et al.* (2007) stated no significant difference between using chicken manure fertilizer and untreated fertilizer.

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Except for the dry and fresh weight data, the manure dose had no significant effect on any observed variables. Further testing revealed a positive linear pattern association, meaning that application of chicken manure will increase the fresh weight of tomato.

The Effect of Variety on Tomato Plant Growth and Yield

Table 2 shows the results of the Least Significant Difference (LSD) on tomato plant growth and yield. The time of flowering and harvesting differed significantly between varieties.

Table 2. Effect of varieties on tomato flowering and harvest time

Varieties	Flowering (DAP)	Harvest (DAP)
Tymoti	28,55 c	52,11 b
Servo	30,33 b	52,44 b
Permata	32,77 a	57,00 a

Note: The numbers followed by different letters in the same column are significantly different at 5% BNT

The Tymoti cultivar has the shortest flowering time than the Servo and Permata varieties. According to the description, the Tymoti variety has the shortest flowering period (28-30 DAP) than the Servo and Permata varieties. Furthermore, genetic and environmental factors influence flowering time. Arnanto *et al.* (2013) reported in their study that the variation in flowering age in each plant is determined not only by genes but also by environmental factors such as temperature, light, and nutrients absorbed by plants.

The Tymoti variety had the shortest harvest time. Still, it was not significantly different from the Servo variety, whereas the Permata variety had the most prolonged harvest age and was considerably different from the Tymoti and Servo varieties. Based on the variety description, the Permata variety had a longer harvest time of 60-70 DAP compared to the Tymoti and Servo varieties. Harvest date is one of the characteristics used to evaluate the superiority of cultivars (Syukur *et al.*, 2012). In this case, there is insufficient evidence to determine the best tomato varieties that can be cultivated in Ultisols. The data analysis revealed that the three varieties studied were not statistically different, implying that all three had the same potential to cultivate in Ultisols. The potential yields obtained were essentially the same between types.

Conclusions

1. There were differences in the response patterns of cultivars to increasing the dose of chicken manure on plant height, dry weight, fruit/plant weight, fruit diameter, and the number of fruits/plants.
2. The optimum chicken manure dose for the growth and yield of tomato plants in Ultisols has yet to be determined.
3. The three tomato varieties, Tymoti, Servo, and Permata, are all suitable for growing in Ultisols.

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